

DETERMINANTS OF FIRM VALUE USING EARNINGS MANAGEMENT AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF FOOD & BEVERAGE CONSUMER INDUSTRY COMPANIES LISTED ON THE INDONESIA STOCK EXCHANGE

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Abstract

The study aims to analyze and address the research gap among previous researchers, as well as the phenomenon of firm value, with Tobin's Q as the proxy, using earnings management as an intervening variable. This research is a quantitative descriptive study using multiple regression analysis with panel data as the basis of analysis. The research object is food and beverage companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. A purposive sampling method was used to determine the sample size, resulting in a cross-section of twenty-six companies observed, with a five-year time series. Furthermore, this study did not produce firm value maximization through earnings management. This study uses a two-model integrated approach, each of which undergoes model selection testing: the Chow Test, the Hausman Test, and the Lagrange Multiplier Tests. The results of the first model, which uses endogenous earnings management variables, indicate that, in addition to institutional ownership and capital structure, all exogenous variables significantly explain earnings management, with the highest sensitivity to the profitability variable ROA. The results of the second model, which uses firm value as a proxy for Tobin's Q as an endogenous variable, show that profitability, ROA, and inflation significantly explain the effect on firm value. The highest sensitivity is found in ROA profitability, while other exogenous variables fail to explain the effect. These results are expected to serve as a guide for public companies in achieving market appreciation in firm value.

Keywords: Firm Value, Earnings Management, ROA Profitability, Inflation, Exchange Rate.

INTRODUCTION DAN LITERATURE REVIEW

A high company value is the hope of business owners because it reflects high shareholder prosperity. Therefore, many investors are interested in purchasing the company's shares, thus increasing demand for the company's shares. Investors will be cautious in making investments to avoid losses. Investors who own shares in a company expect the stock price to continue to rise, as this provides an opportunity for capital gains. Investors can use several methods to measure a company's value when deciding whether to invest. One method used to measure the value of a business is calculating Tobin's Q. (Risman, 2023) writes that Tobin's Q is used as a proxy for company value, defining company value as the market value (stock and debt) of the company and the company's growth potential. The Tobin's Q ratio is considered superior to the market value to book value ratio because it focuses on how much the company is currently worth compared to what it would cost to replace it now. Furthermore, the Tobin's Q ratio is a

more accurate measure of how efficiently management is using the financial resources under its control.

Many factors influence company value, as previously noted by researchers. Inflation, BI interest rates, profitability, and financial risk influence company value (Yuniari et al., 2023). Earnings management, capital structure, and profitability influence company value (E. Y. Putri et al., 2021). Investing in high ESG performance promises financial returns for the firm in terms of both value and profitability (Aydogmus et al., 2022). Meanwhile, according to (Lifaldi et al., 2023), firm value is influenced by institutional ownership, company diversification, and profitability. Furthermore, inflation, interest rates, and exchange rates influence company value in food and beverage sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (Murjiani & Adiyanto, 2023). Financial reporting of a company's operational activities and performance for internal and external parties uses profit/earnings parameters. Profit information available in financial statements is crucial and serves as a basis for investors in making investment decisions.

Earnings management occurs when managers exercise discretion in financial reporting by modifying financial statements to provide convincing results to stakeholders regarding the company's economic performance or to influence contractual outcomes that depend on reported accounting figures. Earnings management is the act of manipulating financial statements by increasing or decreasing earnings, implemented by management through policy choices based on specific interests. Agency conflicts can also result in unethical actions by management by reporting earnings that do not reflect the company's actual performance. Agency theory assumes that principals lack sufficient information regarding the agent's actions, while agents possess more information about their personal skills, work environment, the company as a whole, and future prospects. Thus, the imbalance of information held by principals and agents creates a condition called asymmetric information. This condition encourages managers to conceal information that is not known to shareholders and is used for their own personal gain. Management engages in earnings management to promote the company's image and attract the attention of its users, ultimately increasing the company's value over time. Initially, the company's value will increase over a period of time, but in reality, earnings management can decrease the company's value in the future. Surayya et al. (2023) states that earnings management is crucial as it can affect financial reporting practices and mislead decision-makers. Managers can be influenced by several factors when they engage in earnings management practices. Research by Sinatraz & Sugi (2021) and Jami & Faunti (2021) found that earnings management negatively impacts firm value. Different results were obtained by Riswandi & Yuniarti (2020), E. Y. Putri et al. (2021), and Priyanto & Aryati (2023), which found that earnings management positively impacts firm value. Research related to earnings management by Oktasari (2020) stated that the capital structure, profitability, and size of the company have a positive and significant effect on earnings management. Utami & Hapsari (2022) found that managerial and institutional ownership impact earnings management, and Lock et al. (2019) argued that exchange rate movements contribute to earnings management by firms when exchange rates weaken.

A company's ability to generate net income is related to sales, asset volume, and equity, which constitutes profitability. A company's ability to generate profits is a primary focus when evaluating its performance. Financial performance is one way a company measures its performance (Lifaldi et al., 2023). Competition in the business world is a strong incentive for company management to demonstrate its best performance. Generally, a company's profitability can be used as an indicator to gauge its efficiency. The higher a company's profitability, the better its profit-generating performance. When linked to earnings management, profitability can influence managers to engage in earnings management. When a company's profitability is low, managers generally engage in earnings management to safeguard its performance in the eyes of investors. This is closely related to managers' efforts to demonstrate the best results from the companies they manage. It can also be said that "Good corporate profits tend to reduce management motivation in performing earnings management practices" (Kalbuana et al., 2022). This statement aligns with research by Saniamisha & Jin (2019) and Kalbuana et al., (2022), which found that profitability has a positive effect on earnings management. Furthermore, according to Yovianti & Dermawan (2020), profitability has a significant negative effect on earnings management. This contrasts with research by Wowor et al., (2021), Gozali et al., (2021), and Prawida & Sutrisno (2021), which states that profitability has no effect on earnings management.

A company's going concern must be maintained, especially when the business is profitable, as it is not difficult for a company to obtain capital from investors. Profit reflects management's performance in running a business. High profits can indicate good prospects for the company, which will lead to a positive investor reaction and an increase in stock prices. The better the profitability growth, the better the company's future prospects. Companies with good future prospects also have a higher value in the eyes of investors. When company profits increase, stock prices also have the potential to rise. This allows creditors, suppliers, and investors to assess the company's potential profits from sales and investments. Rising stock prices reflect the company's positive value in the eyes of investors. Research by S. Anggraini & Indrawati (2021), Akhmadi & Januarsi (2021) found that profitability has a positive effect on company value, consistent with research by Hasanudin et al. (2022), and Yuniari et al. (2023). Another finding is the research by Rohim et al. (2019), Ginting (2021), Wibisono & Andesto (2023) found that profitability has a significant negative effect on company value. However, very different results were found by Savitri et al. (2021), Hidayat & Khotimah (2022), who found that profitability had no effect on company firm value.

Institutional ownership refers to the portion of a company's shares owned by institutions (insurance companies, banks, investment firms, and other institutional ownership), according to Yovianti & Dermawan (2020). Institutional ownership is seen as an effective monitoring tool for companies, as it plays a crucial role in monitoring opportunistic management behavior, specifically managers who report profits opportunistically to maximize their personal gain. Sofia & Murwaningsari (2019) argue that higher institutional ownership reduces the opportunity for company management to practice earnings management. Ali et al. (2024) also argue that firms with low institutional ownership manage more earnings compared to firms with high institutional ownership. However, institutional ownership can sometimes make

managers feel obligated to meet the investor's profit objectives. To ensure their performance is deemed good in managing the company, managers may still be inclined to engage in earnings manipulation. Related to this statement, research conducted by Sofia & Murwaningsari (2019), Yovianti & Dermawan (2020) stated that institutional ownership has a significant and negative effect on earnings management. However, this is different from research conducted by Saniamisha & Jin (2019), Cinthya et al., (2022), Febianti et al., (2024) which concluded that institutional ownership has no effect on earnings management. Supervision carried out by institutions is one way to reduce agency conflicts that occur between agents and principals, Jensen & Meckling (1976). Institutional ownership plays an influential role in monitoring management discretion and enhances information competition in capital markets (Widagdo et al.) (2021). Institutional investors have the ability to monitor management more effectively and encourage decision-making that increases company value. As stated by Hong & Linh (2023), independent institutional investors monitor the company and their investment more effectively, allowing them to significantly influence management decisions and improve shareholder value. This control certainly guarantees wealth for shareholders, so that the company's value in the eyes of investors will increase. If institutional investors are dissatisfied with the manager's performance, they can sell their shares. Institutional shareholders in large proportions have greater power and incentives to direct management to maximize company value and maximize shareholders, Jensen & Meckling (1976). Research conducted by Asnawi et al., (2019), Tubagus & Khuzaini, (2020) states that institutional ownership has a positive effect on company value. Meanwhile, the results of research by Isnawati & Widjajanti (2019), Sudiyatno et al., (2023) that institutional ownership does not affect company value. Every business will certainly require capital for its operational activities. This capital can come from owners or shareholders (equity) which is called equity. In addition, capital can also be obtained from loans, which is called foreign capital. There must be a good balance between own and foreign capital. This balance between equity and external capital is called capital structure. Short-run decisions are enveloped by the long-term perspective of a firm, of which the most important dimensions are flexibility and credit risk. During the initiation stage of business, restructuring, or liquidation, all sources of capital can be changed or adapted but not otherwise. The risk and uncertainty of the obligations arising out of capital sources increase as we go further in time. For the same reason, equity funding is considered more risky than debt, Agarwal, (2013)

Fahmi (Amelia & Anhar, 2019) wrote that capital structure is the composition of common stock, preferred stock, and various other classes, retained earnings, and long-term debt maintained by a business entity to finance assets. Companies with a higher proportion of debt compared to their assets tend to manipulate earnings through earnings management. This is done to cover the high debt with high profits, attracting investors. As stated by Sofia & Murwaningsari (2019), companies with a high degree of leverage face a high default risk. The company will not be able to fulfill its obligations, so it seeks earnings management. Furthermore, higher debt will affect the amount of net profit distributed to shareholders, including dividends, because the company will prioritize debt repayment. This can encourage management to engage in earnings management because the company must finance shareholders with its profits, thus maximizing capital utilization to maximize profits. Thus, the

company gains a good image from existing and potential investors, encouraging them to continue investing in the company. This is reinforced by Sofia & Murwaningsari (2019), Oktasari (2020), and Crislianto & Darma (2023), who found that the capital structure variable has a significant effect on the positive direction of earnings management. However, Hapsoro & Bahantwelu (2020), Munoz Mendoza et al. (2021), and Naz & Sheikh (2023) found that capital structure has a negative effect on real earnings management. Furthermore, research by Yanto & Wati (2020) and Febianti et al. (2024) also found no effect of capital structure on earnings management.

Capital structure decisions can impact firm value. From a management perspective, a firm's value can provide an indication of investors' perceptions of a company's past performance and future prospects. Capital structure management aims to create a combination of long-term funding sources to maximize stock prices, which reflect firm value. Firm value will increase if the company's stock price also increases. S. Anggraini & Indrawati (2021) suggest that an increase in company value can occur due to an increase in the amount used by company management for business expansion. When linked to signaling theory, high debt use can be considered a positive signal to the market that management believes in the company's future prospects. However, if debt is too large, this can increase financial risk and be an indication of poor company performance, thereby reducing investor confidence. Amelia & Anhar (2019), Pasaribu et al. (2019), Alhamid & Wahyudi (2023) state that capital structure has a positive effect on company value, but LUU (2021), Febrianti et al., (2024) say that capital structure shows a negative correlation with firm value. Research results in Ferriswara et al., (2022), Warisman & P, (2022), Hasanudin et al., (2022), A. Hakim, (2022) conclude that capital structure does not affect firm value.

The macroeconomic environment is the environment that influences a company's operational activities. The macroeconomic environment encompasses economic prosperity and recession, the production of goods and services within the economy, the rate of production growth, inflation, unemployment, and the balance of payments and exchange rates. Inflation refers to a general and persistent increase in the prices of goods and services over a period of time. However, a price increase for just one or two items cannot be considered inflation unless the increase spreads and/or results in price increases for other goods. The impact of accelerating inflation is felt by businesses worldwide. The consumer sector is also highly dependent on inflation, as this sector is related to people's daily needs and is therefore sensitive to inflationary fluctuations. Companies cannot address inflationary conditions when managing their performance. Rising inflation can result in companies earning small profits. In this case, company management will consider reporting financial statements when inflation increases. Healthy inflation increases wages and company profitability and keeps capital flowing in a growing economy. However, if inflation negatively impacts the business, management may engage in earnings management practices. Research by Rahayu & Emarawati (2024) concluded that inflation had a positive effect on earnings management, while research by Silfiana et al. (2020) stated that inflation had no effect on earnings management. Fluctuations in inflation are a factor investors consider when investing in a company. According to signaling theory, high inflation sends a negative signal to investors. Conversely, Zuhro & Irsad (2022) and Nurdina

et al. (2024) also note that inflation has a significant impact on investor decisions. High inflation makes stock markets less liquid and smaller, while low inflation tends to maintain stock price stability in capital markets. This can mean that inflation is inversely proportional to company value, where a low and relatively stable inflation rate can provide investors with ample funds and opportunities to invest, thus attracting investors to invest their funds in the company's shares. If inflation is still mild, companies may increase the prices of goods or services to accommodate the increase in production costs due to inflation. This price increase can increase company profits. Furthermore, the company's development can be considered good, so its stock price can also increase. This is different when inflation is too high and difficult to control.

This condition can depreciate the currency due to drastic increases in commodity prices. This impact can reduce consumer purchasing power, which in turn can reduce company sales and revenue. In line with signaling theory, findings (Sartika et al., 2019) indicate that inflation has a negative and significant effect on firm value. However, this is inconsistent with the findings of Sembiring (2021) and Yuniari et al. (2023), whose research found that inflation had a significant positive effect on firm value. This contrasts with findings by Muchtar et al. (2021) and Wibisono & Andesto (2023), which found that inflation did not have a significant effect on firm value. The exchange rate, often referred to as the exchange rate, is the comparison of one country's currency with another country's strong currency. Investors generally use the exchange rate as a reference for investment decisions.

Exchange rate risk is unavoidable if a company engages in financial transactions. Lock et al. (2019) stated that firms in developing countries have limited ability to manage price changes due to their credit constraints and lack of hedging opportunities. Under these conditions, many companies experience unfavorable conditions in reported earnings, so management may engage in earnings management to achieve predetermined financial targets. As stated by Christiawan & Narsa (2020), under Rupiah depreciation, managers of firms with foreign currency assets exceeding liabilities are more aggressive in managing earnings than those with higher foreign currency liabilities in Indonesia. The exchange rate is a crucial factor for companies engaged in manufacturing because it is closely related to the company's production costs and expenses. If the rupiah depreciates, production costs, including imported raw materials, will increase, increasing costs and subsequently reducing company profits. The decline in profits makes companies.

For retail businesses that rely heavily on imported suppliers, determining domestic selling prices will be a challenge. If the selling price of a product is high, the theoretical impact is a decrease in people's purchasing power, and if purchasing power weakens, it will impact the company's profits. When a company's profits decline, the company's stock price also decreases, which also impacts the company's value. This statement is in line with Natasiya & Idayati (2020), whose research stated that the exchange rate has a positive and significant effect on firm value. Likewise, Sembiring (2021) found that the exchange rate has a significant positive effect on firm value.

However, research by Muchtar et al. (2021) found that the exchange rate had a significant negative effect on the value of goods and consumption companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. This contrasts with the research results of Sartika et al. (2019), Rumengan et al. (2020), and Wibisono & Andesto (2023), which stated that the exchange rate has no effect on firm value..

HYPOTHESIS

- H1 : There is an influence of ROA Profitability on Earnings Management.
- H2 : There is an influence of Institutional Ownership on Earnings Management.
- H3 : There is an influence of Capital Structure on Earnings Management.
- H4 : There is an influence of inflation on Earnings Management.
- H5 : There is an influence of the Exchange Rate on Earnings Management.
- H6 : There is an influence of ROA Profitability on Firm Value.
- H7 : There is an influence of Institutional Ownership on Firm Value.
- H8 : There is an influence of the Capital Structure Ratio on Firm Value.
- H9 : There is an influence of inflation on firm value.
- H10 : There is an influence of the Exchange Rate on Firm Value.
- H11 : There is an influence of Earnings Management on Firm Value.

Figure 1: Research Framework

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a quantitative descriptive approach with the analysis method used is multiple linear regression of panel data using a combination of five-year time series data or the period 2019 - 2023 or 5 years and a cross section of 26 selected companies as research samples. This study uses objects of Food & Beverage Consumption Industry Manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange with a population of all companies listed in the Food and Beverage sector of 95 companies..

Operational Variables:

Table 1: Operational Variables

No	Variables	Notation	Formulas
1	Profitability	ROA _{it}	$\frac{\text{Earning after tax}}{\text{Total Assets}}$
2	Institutional Ownership	KI _{it}	$\frac{\text{Total Institutional Ownership}}{\text{Number of Shares Outstanding}}$
3	Capital Structure	DER _{it}	$\frac{\text{Debt}}{\text{Equity}}$
4	Inflation	INF _t	$= \frac{\text{IHK}_t - \text{IHK}_{t-1}}{\text{IHK}_{t-1}}$
5	Exchange Rate	KURS _t	$\frac{\text{Kurs}_t - \text{Kurs}_{(t-1)}}{\text{Kurs}_{(t-1)}}$
6	Earnings Management	EM _{it}	$DA_{it} = \left(\frac{TAC_{it}}{TA_{t-1}} \right) - NDA_{it}$
7	Firm Value	Tobin's Q _{it}	$\frac{\text{MVE} + \text{D}}{\text{TA}}$ *MVE= Market Value Equity *D= Debt *TA= Total Assets

Panel Data Multiple Regression Estimation

To perform panel data multiple regression estimation, first ensure the availability of a combination of time series and cross-sectional data. The following approaches can be used to analyze time series and cross-sectional data:

- 1) Common Effect Model (CEM)
- 2) Fixed Effect Model (FEM)
- 3) Random Effect Model (REM)

Model Selection Test

After the three basic analyses mentioned above have been used, three further model fit testing procedures can be performed to select the best panel data multiple regression model, as follows:

Chow Test

The F-statistic is the standard used to determine the choice between the Common Effect model and the Fixed Effect model. Acceptance or rejection of the hypothesis is based on the $\alpha = 5\%$ level for the null hypothesis (H_0) and the alternative hypothesis (H_a). Each of the two models

above will technically compare the F-statistic calculation with the F-table. The result of the calculated $F <$ from the F table will reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and conversely will accept the alternative hypothesis (H_a). Thus, the appropriate model to use is the Fixed Effect Model, the decision will be taken otherwise if the results are different.

Hausman Test

The Hausman test will determine whether to choose a Fixed Effects Model or a Random Effects Model. The Chi-Square statistical distribution with k degrees of freedom, representing the number of exogenous variables, is used as the basis for the test.

The result will accept the null hypothesis (H_0) and reject the alternative hypothesis (H_a). The model is then considered fit and uses a Random Effects Model. Conversely, the Fixed Effects Model will be used if the statistical hypothesis rejects the null hypothesis (H_0) and accepts the alternative hypothesis (H_a).

Uji Lagrange Multiplier (LM)

Determining model fit in the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) involves selecting between the Common Effects Model and the Random Effects Model. The test is based on the Chi-Squares distribution, with degrees of freedom equal to the number of exogenous variables.

If the LM statistic is greater than the critical value of the Chi-Squares statistic, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted. This means that the Random Effects Model is the most suitable estimate. Conversely, if the LM statistic is less than the critical value of the Chi-Squares statistic, the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is rejected. This means that the Common Effects Model is more appropriate..

Panel Data Regression Model

Structural Equations of Research Model I,

$$EM_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1ROA_{it} + \beta_2KI_{it} + \beta_3DER_{it} + \beta_4INF_{it} + \beta_5Kurs_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$i = 1,2,\dots\dots, N ; \quad t = 1,2,\dots\dots T$

Structural Equations of Research Model II,

$$Tobin's Q_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1ROA_{it} + \beta_2KI_{it} + \beta_3DER_{it} + \beta_4INFL_{it} + \beta_5Kurs_{it} + \beta_6EM_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

$i = 1,2,\dots\dots, N ; \quad t = 1,2,\dots\dots, T$

Where:

ROA	=	Profitability		ε	=	Error component
KI	=	Institutional Ownership		β	=	Slope
DER	=	Capital Structure		α	=	Intercept
INF	=	Inflation		N	=	Number of Observations
Kurs	=	Exchange Rate		T	=	Lots of time
EM	=	Earnings Management		NxT	=	Number of Panel Data
Tobin's Q	=	Firm Value				

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

Descriptive Statistics and Model Fit Test

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	ROA	KI	DER	INF	KURS	EM	Tobin's Q
Mean	0.096567	0.649264	0.753068	-0.022551	0.013645	-0.024223	2.065.500
Median	0.084046	0.596200	0.597524	0.026147	0.006775	-0.024698	1.747.449
Maximum	0.416320	0.924610	2.464.993	0.055081	0.100806	0.183275	1.187.782
Minimum	0.000526	0.000000	0.102822	-0.240670	-0.037016	-0.235619	0.578472
Std. Dev.	0.064223	0.212650	0.559055	0.110166	0.047604	0.067763	1.558.434
Skewness	1.505.384	-0.938755	1.004.644	-1.452.202	0.935733	-0.295915	2.727.022
Kurtosis	7.316.165	4.330.731	3.569.443	3.191.764	2.584.973	4.169.618	1.496.750
Jarque-Bera	1.500.092	2.868.608	2.362.480	4.589.185	1.990.427	9.307.285	9.369.084
Probability	0.000000	0.000001	0.000007	0.000000	0.000048	0.009527	0.000000
Sum	1.255.371	8.440.437	9.789.879	-2.931.604	1.773.831	-3.149.049	2.685.150
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.532078	5.833.365	4.031.795	1.565.627	0.292334	0.592344	3.133.044
Observations	130	130	130	130	130	130	130

Source: Processed data

Earnings Management and Firm Value as Endogenous Variables in the Suitability Testing of Research Models I & II.

Table 3: Chow Tests

Research Model I Common Effect Vs Fixed Effect Endogenous Variable: Earnings Management				Research Model II Common Effect Vs Fixed Effect Endogenous Variable: Firm Value			
Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.	Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	3.570718	(25.99)	0.0000	Cross-section F	35.644230	(25.98)	0.0000

Source: Processed data

The results of the Chow-test in Research Model 1 and Research Model 2 yielded statistical hypotheses: rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0) and accepting the alternative hypothesis (H_a) at the $\alpha = 5\%$ level. This suggests that the **Fixed Effect Model** is more appropriate than the Common Effect Model. (Table 3)

Table 4: Hausman Tests

Research Model I Fixed Effect Vs Random Effect Endogenous Variable: Earnings Management				Research Model II Fixed Effect Vs Random Effect Endogenous Variable: Firm Value			
Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.	Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	15.121491	5	0.0099	Cross-section random	11.005981	6	0.0882

Source: Processed data

The results of the Hausman-test in Research Model I and Research Model II produced different research hypotheses. In Research Model I, the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) was accepted at the level of $\alpha = 5\%$, while in Research Model II, the null hypothesis (H_0) was accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) was rejected at the level of $\alpha = 5\%$. This means that the Fixed Effect Model is more suitable for use in Research Model I, while in Research Model II, further paired tests using the Lagrange Multiplier Tests (LM Test) must be carried out (Table-5).

Table 5: Lagrange Multiplier Tests

Research Model II			
Common Effect Vs Random Effect			
Endogenous Variable: Firm Value			
Test Summary	Test Hypothesis		
	Cross-section	Time	Both
Breusch-Pagan	83.93597 (0.0000)	1.495133 (0.2214)	85.43110 (0.0000)

Source: Processed data

The results of the Lagrange Multiplier Tests in Research Model II yielded the following research hypothesis: rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0) and accepting the alternative hypothesis (H_a) at the $\alpha = 5\%$ level. This means that the Random Effect Model is more appropriate than the Common Effect Model. (Table 5).

Table 6: Fixed Effect Model

Endogenous Variable: EM

Total pool (balanced) observations: 130

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.091663	0.074525	-1.229959	0.2216
ROA	0.289304	0.136230	2.123642	0.0362
KI	0.093573	0.105856	0.883968	0.3789
DER	-0.028754	0.023752	-1.210556	0.2289
INF	0.113156	0.029282	3.864376	0.0002
KURS	0.216438	0.065439	3.307472	0.0013
Adjusted R-squared	0.467814			
F-statistic	4.779889; Prob (F-statistic) : 0.000000			

Source: Processed data

Table 7: Random Effect Model

Endogenous Variable: Tobin's Q

Total pool (balanced) observations: 130

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.650898	0.737374	0.882724	0.3791
ROA	12.34568	3.889719	3.173927	0.0019
KI	0.256363	0.663733	0.386244	0.7000
DER	0.062492	0.318161	0.196416	0.8446

INF	-1.049051	0.490587	-2.138359	0.0345
KURS	-1.671294	1.349669	-1.238299	0.2180
EM	-0.332574	1.167093	-0.284960	0.7762
Adjusted R-squared	0.290099			
F-statistic	9.785899; Prob (F-statistic) : 0.000000			

Source: Processed data

- 1: ROA profitability significantly influences Earnings Management with a positive correlation (Table 6).
- 2: Institutional Ownership has an insignificant effect on Earnings Management (Table 6).
- 3: Capital Structure has an insignificant effect on Earnings Management (Table 6).
- 4: Inflation significantly influences Earnings Management with a positive correlation (Table 6).
- 5: Exchange Rate has a significant effect on Earnings Management (Table 6).
- 6: ROA profitability significantly influences Firm Value / Tobin's Q with a positive correlation (Table 7).
- 7: Institutional Ownership has an insignificant effect on Firm Value / Tobin's Q (Table 7).
- 8: Capital Structure has an insignificant effect on Firm Value / Tobin's Q (Table 7).
- 9: Inflation has a significant effect on Firm Value / Tobin's Q (Table 7).
- 10: Exchange Rate has an insignificant effect on Firm Value / Tobin's Q (Table 7).
- 11: Earnings Management has an insignificant effect on Firm Value / Tobin's Q (Table 7).

B. Discussion

This study found that the endogenous Earnings Management variable in the first research model, in addition to the exogenous variables Institutional Ownership and Capital Structure, can explain all exogenous variables on Earnings Management, with the highest sensitivity being the profitability variable ROA, followed by the Exchange Rate and Inflation variables. These results indicate that company management places significant importance on ROA profitability as a micro-fundamental factor, and the Exchange Rate as a macro-fundamental factor in making Earnings Management decisions.

The second research model shows that two exogenous variables, ROA profitability and inflation, can explain the effect on the endogenous variable Firm Value, with Tobin's Q as the proxy, with the highest sensitivity being ROA profitability. These results indicate that both company management and capital market investors share a common perception: ROA profitability is the primary consideration in their decision-making.

The intervening variable Earnings Management used in this study cannot function to mediate the influence of exogenous variables on the endogenous variable Firm Value using the Tobin's Q proxy. Thus, the market reaction that contributes to firm value does not depend on Earnings

Management as a policy taken by the management of companies in the Food and Beverage sector.

CONCLUSION

Findings: The results of this study conclude that Earnings Management as an intervening variable has an insignificant effect on firm value, with Tobin's Q as the proxy, meaning it has no relationship with market appreciation in Food and Beverage sector companies on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. Furthermore, among the exogenous variables used, the one with the highest sensitivity is the Profitability ROA variable. This also serves as a suggestion for future researchers, and especially for company management authorities, regarding the importance of paying attention to the Profitability ROA variable as a key variable for capital market players in the Food and Beverage sector on the Indonesia Stock Exchange.

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